

Multi-compound PFAS transport in the unsaturated zone during infiltration cycles

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HIGHLIGHTS

- PFPeA and PFHxA exhibit tracer-like transport in the unsaturated zone.
- Wetting cycles control the sorption dynamics of PFOA and PFOS.
- Competitive sorption during infiltration affects the PFAS migration sequence.
- Water content variations create dynamic PFAS phase partitioning.
- PFAS dynamic partitioning requires a non-equilibrium-based transport model.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are persistent environmental contaminants known for their long-term retention in subsurface environments. Simultaneous transport of long- and short-chain PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFHxA, and PFPeA) was examined in a large (3 m) column designed to simulate transient flow conditions through episodic infiltration cycles in the unsaturated zone.

Results indicate that short-chained PFAS (PFHxA and PFPeA) exhibited high mobility and minimal retardation, closely matching the transport of a conservative tracer (Bromide). In contrast, long-chained PFAS (PFOS & PFOA) displayed strong retention, with breakthrough curves showing significant delays and concentration fluctuations corresponding to wetting and drainage cycles. Fluctuations in sediment water content, which are attributed to erratic infiltration events, influence PFAS adsorption-desorption dynamics, particularly through solid-phase and air-water interfacial sorption. Flow and transport modeling, which involved equilibrium-based solid phase and air-water interfacial adsorption parameters (K_{AWI} and K_d), underestimates the complex transport of long-chained compounds. The simulations suggest that traditional equilibrium-based models do not fully capture the observed transport under non-steady flow conditions. Accordingly, a conceptual model is proposed to

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explain the interaction between PFAS partitioning and dynamic water content variations, showing how wetting and drainage cycles affect PFAS transition from the solid to the mobile phases.

These findings highlight the crucial role of infiltration-driven processes on PFAS mobility and the need to incorporate non-equilibrium sorption kinetics under transient flow conditions in unsaturated zone modeling. This has important implications for understanding the fate and migration properties of PFAS in the subsurface, providing insights into remediation strategies in contaminated sites.

1. Introduction

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a heterogeneous group of stable and persistent organic pollutants that have been detected in remarkably high concentrations (up to 13,000 µg/L) across global groundwater systems (Chen et al., 2018; Dauchy et al., 2019; Houtz et al., 2013; Rafei and Nejadhashemi, 2023). A significant source of concern for PFAS in the environmental media, amongst other sources (accidental spillage, landfills, and wastewater treatment plants), has been the application of aqueous film-forming foams (AFFFs), leading to the detection in firefighting training and response sites (Adamson et al., 2022; Guelfo and Higgins, 2013; Lyu et al., 2022a). Generally, contaminant migration in the subsurface is governed by the integrated characterization of the porous domain, flow conditions, and the compounds' inherent physicochemical properties, which affect the attenuation properties (Brusseau, et al., 2019b).

Typically, groundwater pollution starts with the downward percolation of contaminated water from the land surface through the unsaturated zone (vadose zone/critical zone) to the underlying groundwater. Hence, the vadose zone is a potential source of long-term PFAS

contaminant influx on the groundwater long after the pollution source has been eliminated from the land surface (Dahan, 2020; Sharifan et al., 2021). Water flow within the unsaturated zone (percolation) is primarily dominated by gravity and capillary forces, generally characterized by a mean vertical flow, with substantial temporal and spatial variability (Berkowitz et al., 2004).

In comparison to other emerging contaminants like fuel oxygenates and chlorinated solvents, PFAS is retained longer and more strongly in the unsaturated zone (Newell et al., 2022). Sorption to the solid matrix, mainly due to hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions, contributes to PFAS long-term retention in the vadose zone (Higgins and Luthy, 2007; Guelfo et al., 2020; Guelfo and Higgins, 2013; Guo and Brusseau, 2024; Higgins and Luthy, 2006; Kookana et al., 2022; Stults et al., 2022; Zeng et al., 2021). Yet, the surfactant characteristics of many PFAS compounds provide an additional attenuation process related to accumulation at the air-water interface (AWI) (Brusseau, 2025; Costanza et al., 2019; Lyu et al., 2018). The chemical structure, such as carbon chain length and functional groups of PFAS, affects their adsorption rates and extent in the vadose zone (Guo and Brusseau, 2024). The magnitude of PFAS retention in the vadose zone also depends on the soil matrix

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration (left) and a picture (right) presenting the distribution of the sampling ports and water content sensors along the column.

heterogeneity and moisture content distribution. Hydrological processes such as precipitation and evapotranspiration directly influence PFAS migration in the unsaturated zone and their subsequent discharge into groundwater. Due to evapotranspiration, PFAS with stronger sorption affinity remain in the aqueous phase due to their low volatility, leading to elevated pore water concentrations and steeper concentration gradients. However, for PFAS compounds with low sorption affinity, evapotranspiration primarily increases their mobile concentrations in pore water. This is due to reduced water content, which expands the air-water interfacial area and consequently provides additional sorption sites for PFAS partitioning at the interface (Feng et al., 2024; Karimi Askarani et al., 2024; Newell et al., 2023; Sharifan et al., 2021; Trobisch et al., 2024; Wallis et al., 2022).

Several studies on PFAS transport in the vadose zone are focused on long-chain 'legacy' PFAS such as PFOA and PFOS (Brusseau, 2019a; Brusseau et al., 2021; Brusseau and Guo, 2021; Brusseau, 2022; Guo et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021). Conversely, less attention has been paid to shorter-chain, AFFF-based contemporary variants like the modern PFAS (PFPeA, PFHxA). Miscible-displacement experiments using small-scale unsaturated and saturated column experiments under steady-state flow conditions have been widely used to quantify PFAS migration rates at the laboratory scale (Supplementary Information) (Bigler et al., 2024; Brusseau et al., 2021; Brusseau et al., 2019a; Garza-Rubalcava et al., 2025; Guelfo et al., 2020; Lyu et al., 2022a, b; Lyu et al., 2018; Lyu and Brusseau, 2020; McKenzie et al., 2016; Park et al., 2020; Röhler et al., 2021; Shea et al., 2025; Stults et al., 2024, 2025; Van Glubt et al., 2021; Vierke et al., 2014; Wanzek et al., 2023).

However, variable and temporal precipitation events are an inherent aspect of the natural environment. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the vertical transport of long-chained PFAS (PFOS and PFOA) and short-chained PFAS (PFHxA and PFPeA) from the land surface to the water table under transient conditions, driven by infiltration events that simulate episodic rainfall. We hypothesize that fluctuations in soil moisture across the vadose zone resulting from these erratic infiltration cycles influence the migration dynamics of PFAS compounds. Consequently, improving the monitoring resolution of multiple PFAS species in the unsaturated zone during percolation events is critical for evaluating the potential for groundwater contamination.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Large-scale column set-up

The experimental setup was designed to enable high-resolution monitoring of PFAS transport across the unsaturated zones during cycles of infiltration events (Fig. 1). The experiments were conducted in a large (3 × 0.4 m) column, mimicking a deep vadose zone overlying groundwater. A drainage outlet from the bottom of the column was set at an elevation of 2.7 m to maintain the water table. Ten custom-made water sampling ports (SP) and seven water content sensors (Acclima TDT) were distributed (embedded horizontally) along the unsaturated section of the column to determine PFAS breakthrough and infiltration conditions. The suction cups have high air entry pressure (1–1.5 bar) with low internal dead volume (3–6 ml) operated through low-diameter tubing (1.9 internal diameter). In addition, ten soil sampling ports enabled the determination of the total PFAS content along the unsaturated profile at the end of the experiment. Water infiltration and PFAS solutions were introduced at the column top using a dripping system of spatial distribution.

The column was packed carefully with sieved sediment collected from a sand dune (Nahal Secher Hills, Negev, Israel). Soil parameters: (1) 92 % sand, 1 % silt, and 7 % clay, (2) bulk density 1.58 kg m⁻³, (3) pH 8.33, (4) EC 743 µs/cm, (5) cation exchange capacity 3.54 meq/100 g, (6) total organic matter content 0.5 %, (7) dissolved organic carbon 7.5 mg/g. Additional information on the soil analytical methods is provided in the supplementary information Method S1. Prior to the transport

experiment, the sediment was analyzed for background PFAS, and none was detected. Also, the column was saturated to ensure adequate compaction and determination of the saturated water content (38–40 %).

2.2. PFAS transport experiments

Initially, trial infiltration experiments (with and without tracers) were conducted to achieve repetitive infiltration and wetting sequences that would be used for the PFAS transport experiment. This enabled clear identification of the wetting front propagation across the entire column and to define the minimal infiltration halt that enables full drainage of the column to field capacity water content values. Eventually, an infiltration sequence of 200 mm per cycle, applied at a rate of 20 mm/h for 10 h, in 72 h cycles was selected. It is important to note that these infiltration conditions represent extreme precipitation events in comparison to natural precipitation. However, it is designed mainly to study transport under sequential wetting and drainage cycles as naturally occurs during rain events. The PFAS transport experiment involved a single short pulse application of a multi-component PFAS solution (equivalent to 8 mm) containing PFOS, PFOA, PFHxA, and PFPeA in a concentration of 10 mg/l each and KBr, as a conservative tracer, in a concentration of 1000 mg/l. The selected PFAS input concentration (10 mg/l) was chosen according to the extracted tracer concentration gradients during the infiltration trials, and to explore their potential for surfactant-induced flow (Bigler et al., 2024; Silva et al., 2020). Moreover, this concentration range has been found in several environmental studies (Chen et al., 2018; Dauchy et al., 2019; Houtz et al., 2013). PFAS application, which took place for only several minutes, was immediately followed by a freshwater infiltration event (200 mm) cycle, which continued for 10 h. After that, eight successive infiltration events were conducted (making a total of 9 cycles in 648 h). Porewater samples were collected periodically for PFAS analysis throughout the experiment, and monitoring stopped during the 9th event. Sediment samples were collected once for total PFAS analysis at the end of the experiment. Detailed descriptions of the PFAS analytical methods, materials, instruments, and quality control are presented in supplementary information (Texts S1, S2, and Method S2, respectively).

The temporal variations in the sediment-water content were analyzed to measure the percolation. The downward flux was calculated from the wetting front propagation velocity and the measured change in water content (Dahan et al., 2008; Rimon et al., 2007). The mass balance recovery (M_{BTC}) for the solutes (PFOS, PFOA, PFHxA, PFPeA, and Br) was estimated using Eq. (1):

$$M_{BTC(\%)} = \frac{\sum (Q_{max} * C * T)}{M_{input}} * 100 \quad (1)$$

M_{BTC} = The total mass of solute exiting each depth as expressed as a percentage of the input mass (M_{input}); Q_{max} = Max. Flow rate of water to the column; C = measured concentration at each point, and T = Time interval between sampling points.

2.3. Transport model

To gain further insights into the dominant transport processes of PFAS, HYDRUS software was used to model 1-D transport of long-chain PFOA and PFOS in the unsaturated zone (Silva et al., 2020; Vahedian et al., 2024a). The model uses the Richards equation to simulate solute transport based on the advection-dispersion equation. A PFAS module explicitly incorporates sorption at the air-water interface (AWI) and accounts for the influence of PFAS concentrations on surface tension. The model allows for both equilibrium and nonequilibrium partitioning between the aqueous and sorbed phases, while assuming equilibrium interactions between the aqueous phase and AWI. Interfacial sorption is represented using the Langmuir isotherm, and the AWI area is

dynamically determined as a function of water content based on the soil water retention curve (SWRC). A comprehensive description of the HYDRUS PFAS module, including the governing equations, was provided in [Silva et al. \(2020\)](#), [Vahedian et al. \(2024a\)](#).

The model domain was constructed according to the column dimension and actual sampling ports distribution ([Fig. 1](#)). Flow and transport parameters were based on experimental conditions. At the same time, adsorption coefficients (K_d and K_{AWI}) were adopted from [Nguyen et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Silva et al. \(2020, 2021\)](#). For PFOA, K_d and K_{AWI} were 0.58 and 0.00369; for PFOS, 3.2 and 0.04795, respectively. Flow boundary conditions were atmospheric at the top and constant pressure head at the bottom; solute transport boundary conditions were solute flux at the top and free drainage at the bottom. Surface tension and viscosity effects were neglected due to the low input concentrations (10 mg/L) ([Silva et al., 2020](#)).

To measure the quality of fit for water content and bromide transport, Root Mean Square Estimation (RMSE) was conducted using [Eq. \(2\)](#):

$$RMSE : \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - O_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

Where P_i = predicted value, O_i = Observed value, and n = number of data points

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Water percolation

Continuous monitoring of variations in water content across the column showed sequential wetting and drainage cycles, which were associated with the infiltration events ([Figs. 2a & 3a](#)). Each wetting cycle was characterized by three distinct phases: (1) sequential rapid rise in

water content, which indicates the wetting front propagation velocity, (2) steady high-water content, which represents a quasi-steady state percolation under unsaturated conditions, and (3) sequential drainage, which is characterized by gradual decreases in water content. The wetting and drainage 3-day cycles showed a consistent repeating pattern throughout the experiment ([Fig. 3a](#)). Up to a depth of 1.95 m, water content values ranged between 0.105 and 0.27, denoting unsaturated conditions. However, at 2.2 m, which is located 0.5 m above the water table, saturation conditions (0.38) prevailed through the entire experiment, denoting the capillary fringe ([Figs. 2a & 3a](#)).

Wetting and drainage cycles facilitate the direct calculation of the wetting front propagation velocity (WFFV) and flux ([Table 1](#)). These velocities represent peak values associated with the wetting front movement down the profile at a specific hydraulic stage. Obviously, these values are not constant and change according to the water application and percolation conditions. Overall, the average wetting front propagation velocity and volumetric flux are 0.2 m/hr and 0.0175 m/hr ([Table 1](#)), respectively, which are comparable to the maximum input rate measured at the dripper outlet (0.022 m/hr).

Bromide (Br) breakthrough curves provide insight into water flow velocities and solute transport across the unsaturated and saturated profile ([Fig. 2b](#)). Each curve reflects transport conditions at different depths and is thus associated with different hydraulic conditions along the wetting and drainage cycle. In the upper part of the unsaturated zone (0.1–1.5 m), the Br breakthrough curves are rather sharp, denoting quick transport in velocities ranging from 0.128 to 0.148 m/h ([Fig. 2b](#) and [Table 1](#)). However, in later times, once the infiltration stopped and the water content started to drop, the breakthrough in the deeper parts (1.8–2.1 m) became wider, reflecting lower fluxes of 0.116 to 0.089 m/h. A delayed breakthrough was observed as the Br approached the saturated parts of the column in the capillary fringe (2.1–2.3 m). Here, the breakthrough was characterized by broad

Fig. 2. (a) Wetting Front Propagation in the First 100 H of the experiment, along with the breakthrough of (b) Bromide, (c) PFPeA, and (d) PFHxA.

Table 1

Wetting Front Propagation Velocities and Flux, Transport Velocities and relative retardation for Bromide, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFOA, and PFOS from the first infiltration phase.

Depth (m)	Wetting front velocity (m/hr)	Flux (m/hr)	Transport Velocity (m/hr)					Relative Retardation (RR)			
			Br	PFPeA	PFHxA	PFOA	PFOS	PFPeA	PFHxA	PFOA	PFOS
0.2	0.111	0.008									
0.3			0.144	0.144	0.124	0.083	0.0013	1.16	1.16	37	73
0.65	0.294	0.026									
0.5			0.143	0.143	0.125	0.004	0.002	1	1.14	23	63
0.8			0.128	0.141	0.11	0.006	–	0.91	1.16	26	–
0.95	0.256	0.025									
1.3	0.135	0.014									
1.15			0.148	0.131	0.112	0.005	–	1.13	1.32	30	–
1.5			0.128	0.128	0.103	0.005	–	1	1.23	38	–
1.65	0.236	0.023									
1.8			0.116	0.124	0.08	0.003	–	0.94	1.45	38	–
1.95	0.15	0.009									
2.1			0.089	0.089	0.04	–	–	1	2.23	–	–
2.3			0.049	0.038	0.027	–	–	1.3	1.83	–	–
2.5			0.029	0.0288	0.028	–	–	1.02	1.04	–	–
Average	0.2	0.0175	0.108	0.107	0.083	0.0176	0.00165	1.05	1.395	32	68

and flat curves, representing the final stages of drainage when water is kept relatively steady at reduced fluxes. Nevertheless, a complete breakthrough and washout of Br from the unsaturated and saturated parts of the column were achieved after the second infiltration event was launched and an infiltration event crossed the entire column, allowing the drainage of the saturated part of the column as expressed from the breakthrough at a depth of 2.5 m. From then on, through the following seven infiltration events (600 h), no traces of Br were found across the column, signifying a complete washout.

3.2. PFAS transport

3.2.1. Short-chain PFAS transport behavior

Transport of PFPeA and PFHxA, as expressed from the breakthrough, exhibits only slight retardation in comparison to Br (Figs. 2c and 2d). Delayed breakthroughs of PFPeA and PFHxA, which are considered short PFAS compounds (C5 and C6), are more pronounced with depth in later times upon flux reduction, particularly near the capillary fringe in later times. Complete breakthrough of both compounds and Br from the entire profile (unsaturated and saturated) was achieved after the second infiltration event (72 h). Transport velocities, as estimated from the breakthrough, closely matched Br, confirming high mobility with minimal retardation (Table 1). Below 1.95 m, reduced velocities, which are attributed to increased saturation, were recorded. Comparing the transport velocity of the PFAS compounds to Br enabled calculation of the Relative Retardation (RR). Apparently, the RR values for PFPeA and PFHxA seem relatively low, 1.02 and 1.24, respectively, which indicates transport behavior nearly identical to Br (Table 1).

The sorption of short-chain PFAS, such as PFPeA and PFHxA, is primarily governed by electrostatic interactions (Li et al., 2023). Hence, the low CEC of the sediment has likely enhanced the rapid transport of PFPeA. Previous studies on PFAS transport in saturated conditions report low soil-water distribution coefficients for PFPeA ($K_d = 0.06 \pm 0.02$ L/kg) and PFHxA ($K_d = 0.08 \pm 0.02$ L/kg) in soils with properties similar to those in our experiment (Nguyen et al., 2020). While single-component air-water interfacial Langmuir coefficients (K_L) for PFPeA are relatively low ($7.75 \pm 0.34 \times 10^1$ L/mol), multi-component systems exhibit increased K_L values due to competitive adsorption (Silva et al., 2021). Consequently, the enhanced adsorption of more surface-active PFAS, such as PFOA and PFOS, promotes the faster migration of less surface-active species like PFPeA and PFHxA.

Under the quasi-steady-state conditions phase of the first infiltration event, the Br breakthrough displayed a relatively low maximum C/Co range of 0.12 to 0.18. However, a steadily constant C/Co was observed between 0.5 and 1.5 m, validating quasi-steady-state flow. In contrast,

the breakthrough of PFPeA and PFHxA exhibited higher maximum C/Co values, ranging from 0.38 to 0.72 and 0.32 to 0.52, respectively. Similarly, a high C/Co of 0.75 to 0.86 was recorded in a saturated adsorption experiment for PFPeA, showing low sorption similarities in both saturated and unsaturated domains (Li et al., 2019). As sandy surfaces are typically negatively charged or neutral, especially at neutral to alkaline pH, which means electrostatic attraction between sand and negatively charged short-chain PFAS is weak or absent. Consequently, Bromide ions (Br^-) are also negatively charged and will not adsorb strongly to sand surfaces, but their presence increases the overall ionic strength of the solution. Hence, the influence of an increase in the ionic strength may inhibit the adsorption of PFPeA and PFHxA at the solid-liquid interface by compressing the electrical double layer at any charged surfaces, further reducing the already weak electrostatic interactions between short-chain PFAS and sand (Molé et al., 2024). This may have further contributed to the high C/Co recorded for PFPeA and PFHxA and their rapid migration close to a conservative tracer. Nevertheless, although the Br contribution to the ionic strength initially reached 1.1 mM, its actual impact on ionic strength continually changed according to the concentration breakthrough. Overall, the sorption of short-chain PFAS in sand is mainly driven by weak hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions, with short-chain PFAS showing very low affinity (Alves et al., 2020; Cai et al., 2022; Molé et al., 2024; Oliver et al., 2020; Smaili and Ng, 2023; Umeh et al., 2023).

The mass balance recovery calculation was calculated from the BTCs for the first 1.15 m of the column, where the breakthrough was still under relatively steady flow conditions (Eq. (1)). Note that the actual flow rate (Q) at each depth is smaller than the maximum flow rate due to water distribution during infiltration (Table 1). Yet, for convenience and simplicity, the maximum flow rate (Q_{max}) was used for recovery calculations. However, this may constitute an overestimation of the recovery of the PFAS compounds since transient flow conditions are observable in the unsaturated domain. The average mass recovery of Bromide, PFPeA, and PFHxA for the upper 1.15 m of the unsaturated part of the column was 95, 171, and 139 %, respectively. The calculated recovery of short-chain PFAS compounds is significantly higher than that of the non-reactive tracer. Furthermore, while PFPeA and PFHxA exhibit tracer-like transport, their low reactivity may constitute some adsorption reactions in the unsaturated media. Consequently, delayed desorption time can result in contaminants remaining in the system and later appearing in samples. This delayed desorption creates a kinetic limitation, inflating the apparent recovered mass (Rahman et al., 2004). Additionally, PFAS compounds diffuse into low-permeability matrix areas at low water content, reducing contaminant concentrations in mobile pore-water regions and effectively delaying overall recovery

(Chen and Guo, 2023).

Surface-active organic solutes have been shown to induce faster water flow in unsaturated porous media, with extended velocities along with the pollutant gradient (Henry and Smith, 2003). Moreover, PFAS concentrations exceeding 10 mg/L have been reported to enhance surface tension-induced flow (Silva et al., 2020; Vahedian et al., 2024b). Although a total concentration of 40 mg/L (comprising 10 mg/L each of four individual PFAS compounds) was introduced—an amount that could potentially induce surfactant-driven flow—no observable effects of surfactant-induced flow were detected. A comparison of the wetting front behavior during the initial infiltration with that of prior wetting regimes (from preliminary tests) revealed no noticeable deviation in the wetting front propagation velocity, indicating the absence or minimal effects of surfactant-induced (Marangoni) flow. This outcome is likely attributable to the presence of background KBr, which may have suppressed interfacial tension effects. Notably, the KBr concentration of 1000 mg/L substantially elevated the solution's ionic strength during the first infiltration event, when the tracer was present along with the PFPeA and PFHxA (Lyu and Brusseau, 2020). Similar minimal impact of surfactant-induced flow was also recorded for a PFOS input concentration of 10 mg/L (Bigler et al., 2024). Overall, surfactant-induced flow has been shown to have minimal impact on the long-term leaching of PFAS (Zeng and Guo, 2021).

3.2.2. Long-chain PFAS transport

The transport of PFOA and PFOS, which represent legacy long-chain PFAS (LC-PFAS) compounds of the carboxylic and sulphonic functional head groups, is very different in comparison to short-chain compounds and Br (Fig. 3 and Fig. 2). Apparently, their breakthrough, which is expressed by their concentration in the sediment pore-water, seems to be strongly related to infiltration episodes and increased water content of the sediment. While transport of PFPeA and PFHxA across the saturated and unsaturated part of the column was completed by the second infiltration event, traces of PFOA and PFOS were recorded in the pore water along the column after every infiltration event, even after the ninth

event, which corresponds to 15 pore volumes (Fig. 3). Interestingly, the concentration of these compounds in the sediment pore water was increased and decreased following every infiltration event and corresponding to the wetting and drainage cycles. Both PFOS and PFOA are transported down during high water content periods. Yet, a close look at the PFOA breakthrough curve shows erratic, fluctuating concentration, which does not follow a typical single breakthrough as was found for PFPeA and PFHxA. Fluctuating concentration shows that the transport mechanism is very complex and cannot be explained straightforwardly by the advection-dispersion mechanism. In any event, their transport velocity is orders of magnitude slower and reflects strong retardation, which is water content dependent (Table 1).

PFOA BTCs show partial releases across all depths up to 1.8 m in the first infiltration event (Fig. 3b). However, significant breakthroughs were observed only at shallow depths <0.8 m. The second infiltration event induced partial release of PFOA from 0.3 m to 0.5 m with traces down to a depth of 1.8 m. Partial release of PFOA was observed in all nine monitored infiltration events up to a depth of 2.1 m. In saturated adsorption experiments, the fraction in the liquid phase (C/C_0) was greater than 0.5 for PFOA, reflecting a potential for migration of this compound in saturated conditions (Li et al., 2019). Yet, relative concentrations < 0.5 were observed throughout the experiment, reflecting stronger retardation conditions. Yet, more complexity is expressed through the water content dependency of concentration during the different stages of wetting and drainage cycles.

The soil-water distribution coefficient of PFOA ($K_d = 0.59 \pm 0.28$) is much higher than PFPeA and PFHxA (Nguyen et al., 2020). Similarly, the air-water interfacial adsorption (Langmuir) coefficients are reportedly three orders of magnitude higher than PFPeA ($8.33 \pm 0.33 \times 10^3$ (L/mol)) (Silva et al., 2021). Hence, the partial release of the PFOA across the unsaturated part of the column is attributed to the combined influence of adsorption on the air-water interface (AWI) and the solid phase (K_d). The RR for PFOA shows high values ranging from 22.6 to 38.3, with an average of 31.8 (Table 1), confirming low mobility and significant retardation.

Fig. 3. Breakthrough curve of PFOA and PFOS along with variation in sediment water content during the infiltration cycles. Note that the breakthrough is obtained from the concentration in the sediment pore water samples.

The dynamics of PFOS resemble PFOA mobility, yet with much greater retardation. Despite multiple intense infiltration events, the release of PFOS to the water phase was minimal and limited to the active infiltration phases, which were characterized by high water content (Fig. 3c). PFOS is a very adsorbing compound with a high $K_d = 3.29 \pm 0.88$ (Nguyen et al., 2020) and high Langmuir AWI adsorption coefficient of $K_{AWI} = 1.37 \pm 0.02 \times 10^5$ (L/mol) (Silva et al., 2021). Variations in sediment water content during the infiltration events (Figs. 2a and 3a) show that an increase of 60 % in water saturation, from 0.25 to 0.4, was sufficient to mobilize LC-PFAS. Yet, the potential for its release to the flowing water exists whenever the water content values increase steadily. The PFOS relative retardation ranged between 22 and 75 (with an average of 49.5) times, with <3 % partitioned to the liquid phase. Studies have shown that PFAS sorption at air-water interfaces increases with perfluorinated chain length and similar AWI adsorption with compounds of the same chain length but with different functional groups (Silva et al., 2021).

3.3. Adsorption kinetics and competitive adsorption mechanism for long-chain PFAS

The soil adsorption kinetics for PFAS have been described as biexponential adsorption with adsorption sites characterized by fast and slow sorption rates (Li et al., 2019). A closer look at the breakthrough of

Fig. 4. Breakthrough showing adsorption kinetics and competitive adsorption between PFOA and PFOS during the quasi-steady-state phase of the first infiltration event at various depths.

LC-PFAS during active infiltration events reveals the non-equilibrium kinetics of adsorption. This is characterized by the continual fluctuation of the concentrations of LC-PFAS during steady-state flow conditions (Fig. 4). This paradigm of adsorption kinetics may further facilitate the downward transport of these compounds since equilibrium adsorption has not been reached. Generally, from solid phase adsorption experiments in saturated conditions, PFAS compounds have been found to reach equilibrium at a time of > 7 days (Milinovic et al., 2015). Given that infiltration events have erratic characteristics with quick changes in saturation conditions, PFAS non-equilibrium adsorption mobility dynamics may further contribute to the unstable, erratic transport of PFOA and PFOS down the column with the flowing water.

Competitive sorption effects between PFOA and PFOS were observed during the quasi-steady-state flow phase of the first infiltration event, as shown in the preferential adsorption of LC-PFAS in the first three observed depths (0.1, 0.3, and 0.5 m) (Fig. 4). At a depth of 0.1 m (Fig. 4a), PFOA was released preferentially. In contrast, PFOS release was delayed only to significantly appear 3 h later (Fig. 4a). Deeper in the profile, at 0.3 m (Fig. 4b), PFOA keeps migrating and occupying sorption sites while PFOS is still delayed, revealing minimal release to the pore water. At this stage, PFOA arrives at a destination where minor traces of PFOS can be found, allowing its non-competitive sorption. However, at 0.5 m, a significant release of PFOS was observed 8 h after the contaminant injection, potentially displacing PFOA from the sorption sites (Fig. 4c). This demonstrates the dynamics of the competitive adsorption-desorption mechanisms that involve multiple PFAS compounds, where solutes with higher sorption potential displace those with less sorption potential (Belkouteb et al., 2020; Garza-Rubalcava et al., 2025). Accordingly, it may be hypothesized that PFOA released into the water is due to the strong sorption affinity of PFOS to the solid phase, which inhibits PFOA sorption, as expected from the competitive sorption mechanism. Similar cases were reported as well, where PFOA was preferentially released from competitive sorption between PFOA and PFOS (Abraham et al., 2022; Garza-Rubalcava et al., 2025; Kookana et al., 2022). Consequently, the high sorption affinity of LC-PFAS may have also enhanced the rapid transport of SC-PFAS.

Competitive adsorption between PFOA and PFOS is strongly influenced by their interactions at the air-water interface (AWI), with significant implications for their transport and retention in unsaturated porous media. PFOS has a higher affinity for the AWI than PFOA, leading to stronger retention of PFOS when both are present. This is due to PFOS's greater hydrophobicity and larger molecular size, which enhances its surface activity compared to PFOA (Abraham et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2025; Silva et al., 2021). In binary mixtures, PFOS outcompetes PFOA for adsorption sites at the AWI, resulting in less retention of PFOA than would be expected from single-solute behavior. This manifests as an earlier and sharper breakthrough of PFOA (Abraham et al., 2022; Garza-Rubalcava et al., 2025). Further contribution to the preferential adsorption of PFOS over PFOA to the AWI may be enhanced by the charge shielding effect from positive ions (K^+ from KBr and background ions) accumulating near the negatively charged surfaces, reducing or shielding repulsion (Abraham et al., 2022; Silva et al., 2021). However, considering the scale of our experiment, the influence of charge shielding may likely be unevenly distributed, given the transient flow conditions of the unsaturated region. Furthermore, due to the transient nature of our experimental setup, ionic strength values varied continuously throughout the experiment.

Solid-phase adsorption (to mineral surfaces) contributes less to overall retention for these PFAS, but its relative importance increases as the AWI area decreases due to an increase in water saturation. Similar to the competitive adsorption in the AWI, PFOS was found to competitively displace PFOA at sorption sites on solid surfaces (Cai et al., 2022; Maimaiti et al., 2018). Overall, the changes in the flow dynamics and variable water saturation directly impact the competitive adsorption both to the solid and the AWI surfaces.

Fig. 5. Total mass distribution (+ standard deviation) of PFOA and PFOS across the unsaturated column after 9 infiltration events.

3.4. PFAS adsorption

Following the observations that PFOS and PFOA kept appearing sparsely in the pore water, even after the nine infiltration events, sediment samples were collected to quantify the total PFAS content. As

opposed to the pore water samples (Figs. 2 and 3) that represent the soluble PFAS in the mobile water, the soil extract includes the total PFAS content, which consists of both adsorbed and soluble (Fig. 5). The relative mass here refers to the percentage mass of leached PFAS (from the extracted soil) to the input mass at the beginning of the experiment (Fig. 5). While there were no traces of PFPeA and PFHxA, both PFOA and PFOS exhibited significant migration down the entire column (Fig. 5). While PFOS's central mass was retained at shallow depths (0.1 m), PFOA moved deeper into the profile, with the center of mass at 1.5 m. Although the total PFAS distribution was inferred from a small sample, the calculated mass recovery for PFOA and PFOS yields 105 % and 138 %, respectively, which are reasonable in PFAS analysis.

The soil extracted from the deep sections of the column, which were under saturated conditions (in and below the capillary fringe ~2–2.7 m), show traces of both PFOA and PFOS, indicating active transport (Fig 5). Nevertheless, no traces of these compounds were found in the pore water extracted from these depths (Fig 3), showing strong retention in these regions.

3.5. Transport model

Water content variation with time, along with Br transport, was first simulated to account for the model flow and transport parameters (Fig 6) (Guo et al., 2022; Silva et al., 2020; Vahedian et al., 2024a). Adjusting the model parameter to account for both water content variations and Br breakthrough required a minor compromise on the fitting level of the water content values at a depth of 2.2 m, which appears to be at the top of the capillary fringe. This minor compromise on the fitting level of the water content values near the capillary fringe was made to better match the observed and predicted transport of the Br along the entire column, especially in the unsaturated zone. To account for the water content in the saturated part of the capillary fringe, another sampling point in the model was added at a depth of 2.45 m, which is still 0.25 m above the water table.

The observed and predicted water content in the unsaturated zone shows a good fit, with RMSE ranging between 0.0145 and 0.0238, with similar wetting front arrival times. Simulated Br transport with the Van-Genuchten hydraulic parameters α , n , and dispersivity (λ), which were

Fig. 6. (a) Observed Water Content, (b) Predicted Water Content, (c) Observed Tracer BTCs, (d) Simulated Tracer BTCs.

Fig. 7. Observed and predicted PFOA and PFOS BTCs in simulation considering K_{AWI} Only, K_d Only, combined $K_{AWI} + K_d$, and AWI Kinetic modified combined $K_{AWI} + K_d$.

iteratively adjusted to 0.0265 cm^{-1} , 2.65, and 0.27 m, respectively, resulted in a good fit with RMSE values ranging from 0.022 to 0.147. The close fit of simulated water content and tracer BTCs validates the hydraulic properties of the porous media.

The transport of PFOA and PFOS was first simulated separately for equilibrium air-water interfacial adsorption (K_{AWI}) and solid-phase adsorption (K_d), and then for the combined influence of both K_d and K_{AWI} (Fig. 7). Notably, the influence of competitive adsorption was not considered in the LC-PFAS transport model simulations.

When K_{AWI} alone was considered, PFOA achieved a complete breakthrough across all observation depths within 600 h, with a match of the peaks from 0.1 to 1.5 m (Fig. 7a and c). From the simulation, the maximum air-water interfacial area (AWIA), a function of the water content from the top to 1.5 m, ranged between 245 and $170\text{ cm}^2/\text{cm}^3$ as water content increased. These values are relatively low, considering other sandy textures have been simulated to have interfacial areas of $> 600\text{ cm}^2/\text{cm}^3$ (Guo et al., 2020). Yet, AWI adsorption appears to be the dominant transport process in the upper section of the unsaturated zone ($< 1.5\text{ m}$) for this experiment. In the case where K_d alone was considered in the simulation, PFOA achieved a complete breakthrough from depths of 0 to 1.5 m, and partially at 1.8 m and 2.1 m (Fig. 7e). Comparing the observed and simulated BTC of PFOA with K_d only shows a similar release at 1.5 m to 1.8 m, indicating that solid-phase adsorption dominates PFOA transport in regions of higher water content, where air-water interfacial areas are reduced (Fig. 7e). Combining both K_d and K_{AWI} as adsorption parameters does not provide any improved trend with the observed BTC (Fig. 7g).

Since the observations reveal significant transport of PFOA, which was not predicted by the simulation scenarios, it is assumed that other processes may further contribute to PFOA transport. The influence of competitive adsorption on the solid phase and the AWI, combined with the non-equilibrium adsorption kinetics influence on transient flow and transport under intense erratic infiltration conditions, contributes to the early release of PFOA.

Simulations of PFOS transport, accounting for K_{AWI} , K_d , and the combination of both (Fig. 7d, f, and h), did not align with the observed BTC (Fig. 7b). Experimental studies have shown that the AWI can account for 50–75 % of total retention of PFOA in unsaturated porous media, highlighting the critical role of both the interfacial adsorption compared to solid-phase adsorption (Brusseau, 2018, 2019b; Brusseau and Guo, 2021; Costanza et al., 2019; Lyu et al., 2018, 2022a; Lyu and Brusseau, 2020; Schaefer et al., 2019)

Furthermore, experimental and modeling studies involving homogeneous sandy porous media for PFOA and PFOS, where further inverse solutions provided 48 % and 35 % equilibrium sorption sites. Conversely, the kinetic sites for PFOA and PFOS were 52 and 65 % respectively. This non-equilibrium partitioning was attributed to chemical non-equilibrium processes (kinetics of adsorption/desorption or reactions) (Vahedian et al., 2024a). Accordingly, simulations based on the non-equilibrium partitioning empirical values (F_{aw} and ω) and equilibrium K_d and K_{AWI} were done (Fig. 7i and j). Yet, there was no clear distinct correlation with the observed data.

Analysis of the observed and predicted BTC for both PFOA and PFOS shows that all models predicted complete breakthroughs at certain depths at different times. Nevertheless, the observed BT shows erratic transport with increased concentrations of both PFOA and PFOS at different depths following every infiltration event, and an increase in concentration that follows an increase in water content. This suggests that the PFOA and PFOS transport can't be predicted solely by either the equilibrium sorption coefficient K_{AWI} , K_d , or even by the combination of

both. Additionally, considering the non-equilibrium partitioning sites apparently would require further information on the relationship between water saturation values, physical and chemical non-equilibrium processes. Changing the values of K_{AWI} and K_d would only change the depth or extent of the BTCs, but not the kinetic trends in the model. Yet, there is a clear indication that the impact of increased water content dynamics on the mobility of all these compounds is significant and requires more attention.

3.6. Conceptual model for LC-PFAS transport

This study shows that long-chained PFAS experienced dramatic concentration fluctuations during infiltration cycles (Fig. 3), which were directly linked to changes in water content. Specifically, increased water content was found to induce the release of LC-PFAS, resulting in elevated concentrations in the pore water. As such, a reduction or increase in concentration needs to be related to a mechanism that either removes or adds PFAS mass to the mobile water phase. Theoretically, it is assumed that capillary water and water films are interconnected and maintain dynamic equilibrium (Chen and Guo, 2023). Yet, during drainage and water content reduction, thin water films may be disconnected from the mobile phase (Rimon et al., 2011). Therefore, observed reduction in PFAS concentrations may be attributed to the redistribution of PFAS from the mobile water to the solid surfaces and disconnected water films in drained regions. These drained regions extend whenever water retreats within the pore structure to the thinner portions of the pore space upon water content reduction.

This behavior aligns with known PFAS adsorption-desorption mechanisms in the unsaturated zone, which are closely associated with air-water interfaces in porous media (Shea et al., 2025). In non-saturated sediments, two primary types of air-water interfaces dominate: the bulk capillary interface, characterized by pendular rings, and the thinner water films. Notably, previous studies have underscored the critical role of water film-associated interfaces in PFAS retardation. These thin interfaces become more prominent at low water content, enhancing PFAS retention and contributing to delayed transport (Araujo and Brusseau, 2020; Brusseau, 2018; Brusseau et al., 2007; Chen and Guo, 2023; Peng and Brusseau, 2005)

Here, we propose a conceptual model to explain the complex dynamics of LC-PFAS concentration variation with changes in water content. The model is based on the observed variations in PFOA and PFOS BTCs (Fig. 8). Initially, at high water content (Fig. 8a), LC-PFAS is partially partitioned between the liquid, solid, and air-water interfaces (Fig. 8c). The PFAS concentration in the pore water is at its highest concentration, reflecting the partitioning ratio between the different phases, water, solid, and air interfaces. In the next phase, water content is reduced and retreats to a smaller portion of the pore, leaving PFAS mass on the solid phase surfaces or disconnected water films (Fig. 8b and d). A process that is conceptually analogous to wood debris settling on the riverbanks after a flood retreat. Yet, the adsorption kinetic dynamics and transient flow conditions dictate some of the fluctuations in concentration at any new wetting stage, which is related to the new incoming water to every pore. As such, they may constitute an increase and decrease of LC-PFAS concentration in the porewater. Obviously, the porewater's chemical composition, electrostatic, and media properties contribute to the mobility of these legacy compounds (Cogorno et al., 2025). These processes continue iteratively with the combined effects of erratic infiltration, changes in water content of the unsaturated zone, and physical and chemical non-equilibrium processes until reaching the water table.

Fig. 8. A conceptual model for Long Chain PFAS transport (a) Water content data extracted from the study; (b) Breakthrough curve at the same region; (c) Conceptual model at increased saturation, and (d) Conceptual model at decreased saturation.

4. Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the transport behavior of per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) through the vadose zone under non-steady, transient infiltration conditions. Transport of multi-PFAS compounds was investigated in a 3-meter-long soil column structured as an unsaturated zone overlying a water table and groundwater. The experiment was conducted through a sequence of infiltration cycles that mimic extreme episodic rainfall events. The findings revealed that short-chained PFAS compounds exhibited high mobility with transport velocities nearly identical to that of a conservative tracer (bromide), suggesting negligible retardation and a high risk for groundwater contamination. In contrast, long-chained PFAS showed significantly delayed and dynamic transport behaviors. It has been shown that the water saturation degree of the sediment dynamically influences mobility properties. Moreover, the concentrations of LC-PFAS in pore water fluctuated with the changes in sediment water content. It has been observed that the increase in water content of the sediment during infiltration events resulted in a dramatic increase in concentrations, while declining concentrations were measured during the drainage phase, which is characterized by a reduction in water content. This phenomenon emphasizes the non-equilibrium nature of sorption and desorption processes. Additionally, competitive adsorption between PFOS, which is a strongly reactive compound, enhances the mobility of PFOA.

Transport simulations were conducted using a model calibrated against water flow and conservative tracer transport. The model, which employed equilibrium adsorption coefficients (K_d & K_{AW}), failed to fully capture the complex transport of the long-chained PFAS. An additional model simulation for kinetic AWI partitioning reveals the potential for a combination of both physical and chemical non-equilibrium partitioning in PFAS transport analysis. These modeling limitations highlight the

inadequacy of equilibrium-based assumptions in simulating PFAS transport under realistic field conditions characterized by transient water flow and erratic infiltration events. Traditional equilibrium-based models that fail to capture rate-limited sorption/desorption processes will generally overestimate mass discharge of PFAS into groundwater in the short term but may underestimate it in the long term.

A conceptual model was developed to explain the observed behavior of long-chained PFAS, incorporating water content fluctuations, non-equilibrium sorption kinetics, and phase-specific partitioning. The model suggests that water redistribution during infiltration and drainage phases creates dynamic conditions, influencing PFAS partitioning and availability in the mobile water phase.

Overall, this study highlights the need to incorporate transient flow processes, kinetic sorption, and multi-component interactions into predictive models of PFAS fate and transport in the vadose zone. As such, solutions for assessing the long-term risks of PFAS contamination would be more accurate, providing efficient implementation of remediation strategies in vadose zone environments impacted by AFFF-related or similar PFAS sources.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Samuel Oluwaseun Kolade: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Avner Ronen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Tuvia Turkeltaub:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Data curation. **Christos Tsakiroglou:** Writing – review & editing. **Knud Erik Strøyberg Klint:** Writing – review & editing. **Prerona Das:** Methodology. **Ofer Dahan:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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